
Voynich Manuscript

Verifiable Statistical Observations

Ground Truth from the EVA Corpus

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Abstract. We present a comprehensive statistical analysis of the Voynich Manuscript (Beinecke MS 408) derived entirely from the Zandbergen-Landini EVA transcription (38,222 words, 8,543 unique types, 227 pages). The analysis spans character-level structure (entropy, positional constraints, forbidden bigrams), word-level properties (Zipf distribution, prefix-suffix morphology, length patterns), line- and paragraph-level organization (the Jaccard anomaly, word position effects, repetition patterns), and manuscript-level variation (section vocabularies, Carrier Language A/B, the dense Stars section f103–f116). All quantitative results reported in Sections 1–9 are independently reproducible from the transcription data. Interpretive analysis and open questions are collected separately in Section 10. Definitions of statistical measures are provided in Appendix A.

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1 Introduction and Corpus Summary

1.1 Physical and Historical Context

The Voynich Manuscript (Beinecke MS 408) is an illustrated codex written in an undeciphered script.

- **Radiocarbon dating** of the vellum places the manuscript in the early 15th century, with the 95% confidence interval spanning **1404–1438** and the most probable range centered on **1411–1430** [University of Arizona(2009)].
- **Early known ownership: Holy Roman Emperor Rudolf II** reportedly purchased the manuscript for 600 ducats, according to a 1665 letter from Johannes Marcus Marci to Athanasius Kircher [D’Imperio(1978)]. A faded signature on the first folio identifies **Jacobus Sinapius** (Jacob Tepenecz), an imperial chemist and pharmacist at Rudolf’s court in Prague, as a subsequent owner.
- The **bookbinding** is consistent with 15th-century Central European manufacture, corroborating the radiocarbon date [Beinecke Library].
- **Illustrations precede text:** Throughout the manuscript, the text is clearly *written around* the illustrations—words curve along drawing edges and text blocks are shaped to fit available space. The pictorial program was laid out first; the text was added afterward.
- **Architectural style:** A drawing of castle battlements has been identified as matching the **northern Italian swallowtail merlon** (Ghibelline) style, a distinctive crenellation pattern found in 14th–15th century fortifications in Veneto and Lombardy [Zandbergen(2024)].

1.2 Corpus Summary

All statistics in this paper derive from the Zandbergen-Landini EVA transcription [Zandbergen(2017)] (ZL3b-n.txt).

Metric	Value
Total word tokens	38,222
Unique word types	8,543
Type-token ratio	0.224
Hapax legomena (appear once)	6,088 (71.3% of types)
Dis legomena (appear twice)	886
Total EVA characters	194,305
Unique EVA characters	26
Pages	227
Lines	5,385
Paragraph markers	780 (244 multi-line text paragraphs)

Table 1: Corpus summary statistics.

Observation: Extreme hapax rate

71.3% of all unique word types appear exactly once—6,088 of 8,543 types are singletons. Natural languages typically have hapax rates of 40–50% [Zipf(1935)].

1.3 Top 20 Words

#	Word	Count	#	Word	Count
1	daiin	798	11	qokeey	307
2	ol	552	12	qokeedy	303
3	chedy	502	13	dar	301
4	aiin	499	14	y	296
5	shedy	432	15	qokain	278
6	ar	400	16	shy	271
7	chol	382	17	qokedy	270
8	or	380	18	qokaiin	266
9	chey	350	19	al	256
10	s	309	20	dy	233

Table 2: The 20 most frequent words in the corpus.

2 Character-Level Structure

2.1 Alphabet and Frequencies

Figure 1: EVA character frequency distribution. *o* is the most common character (13.2%).

2.2 Entropy

Metric	Definition	VMS	English	Latin
H_0 (unigram)	$H(c)$	3.87 bits	4.07 bits	4.00 bits
H_1 (bigram/char)	$H(c_1, c_2)/2$	2.83 bits	3.32 bits	3.40 bits
$H(c_2 c_1)$ (conditional)	$2H_1 - H_0$	1.79 bits	~2.57 bits	~2.80 bits
H_2 (trigram/char)	$H(c_1, c_2, c_3)/3$	2.40 bits	~2.80 bits	~2.90 bits

Table 3: Character entropy at multiple n-gram orders. VMS values are consistently below natural language at every level.

Observation: Low character entropy

Bigram entropy per character ($H_1 = 2.83$ bits) is 15% below English and 17% below Latin. Character sequences in VMS are more predictable than in natural language at every n-gram order.

2.3 Character N-Grams

n	Total	Unique	Possible	Util.%	$H(n)$ bits	$H(n)/n$
1	167,745	25	26	96.2	3.863	3.863
2	133,814	265	676	39.2	5.652	2.826
3	101,024	1,277	17,576	7.3	7.204	2.401
4	70,495	3,132	456,976	0.7	8.547	2.137

Table 4: Within-word character n-gram statistics. Utilization drops from 96.2% (unigrams) to 0.7% (quadgrams).

Observation: Extreme bigram constraint

Only 265 of 676 possible character bigrams are attested (39.2% utilization). More than 60% of the character pair space is never used within words.

Observation: Top-30 bigrams cover 78.8% of text

Just 30 character bigrams account for 78.8% of all character content. This concentration is far beyond what natural alphabets produce.

Bigram	Count	%	Bigram	Count	%
ch	9,845	7.36	ee	4,507	3.37
he	7,443	5.56	ii	4,262	3.19
dy	6,190	4.63	sh	4,150	3.10
ai	6,050	4.52	ho	3,660	2.74
in	5,522	4.13	ey	3,624	2.71
ok	5,420	4.05	da	3,554	2.66
qo	5,096	3.81	ke	3,465	2.59
ol	4,968	3.71	od	2,553	1.91
ed	4,666	3.49	ot	2,340	1.75

Table 5: Top 18 character bigrams. The top 10 account for 44.6% of all bigram tokens.

Trigram	Count	%	Quadgram	Count	%
che	4,556	4.51	aiin	3,569	5.06
edy	3,911	3.87	hedy	1,881	2.67
iin	3,897	3.86	ched	1,459	2.07
aii	3,851	3.81	daii	1,388	1.97
qok	3,015	2.98	qoke	1,357	1.92
she	2,397	2.37	okee	1,210	1.72
cho	2,383	2.36	eedy	1,149	1.63
hed	2,279	2.26	okai	997	1.41
oke	2,239	2.22	qoka	995	1.41
dai	1,976	1.96	cheo	954	1.35

Table 6: Top 10 character trigrams and quadgrams. The quadgram `aiin` alone accounts for 5% of all quadgram tokens.

2.4 Forbidden Sequences and Positional Constraints

Of 676 possible character bigrams (26^2 from the EVA alphabet), only 265 are observed within words—60.8% of the bigram space is forbidden.

2.4.1 Dead Characters

Character	Followers	Note
b	0 of 25	Never followed by any character (word-final only, 2 occurrences)
u	0 of 25	Never followed by any character (extremely rare)
v	1 of 25 ($v \rightarrow o$)	Near-dead; only vo is attested
g	2 of 25 ($g \rightarrow a, g \rightarrow o$)	Almost exclusively word-final (91 of 93 occurrences)
j	2 of 25 ($j \rightarrow a, j \rightarrow y$)	Extremely rare
x	3 of 25 ($x \rightarrow a, x \rightarrow o, x \rightarrow y$)	Extremely rare, label-specific

Table 7: Characters with the fewest possible followers.

Observation: Dead zone in the alphabet

Characters b, u, v, x, j, and g together account for fewer than 200 of 194,000 characters. The core functional alphabet contains approximately 19 characters.

2.4.2 Constraints on c

The character c can only be followed by 5 of 25 characters: f, h, k, p, t. It never precedes vowel-like characters (a, e, i, o) or common consonant-like characters (d, l, r, s).

Observation: c is a prefix component

The character c always forms part of a multi-character unit: ch, ck, ct, cp, cf. It is not an independent character but a structural modifier that combines with specific partners.

2.4.3 Double Letters

Bigram	Count	Bigram	Count
ee	4,519	ll	28
ii	4,270	dd	21
oo	68	aa	5
ss	29	rr, hh, mm, tt	1–4 each

Observation: Only ee and ii double freely

ee (4,519) and ii (4,270) are extremely common—accounting for 65% of all occurrences of e and i. No other character doubles with comparable frequency ($oo=68$ is 100x rarer).

2.4.4 Positional Constraints

Character	Initial %	Final %	Ratio	Constraint
q	96.9%	0.0%	∞	Almost exclusively word-initial
y	4.9%	40.3%	0.12	Strongly word-final
n	0.0%	96.3%	0.00	Almost exclusively word-final
m	0.3%	97.3%	0.00	Almost exclusively word-final

Table 8: Characters with extreme positional bias.

Observation: Extreme positional bias

q appears word-initially 96.9% of the time. n and m appear word-finally 96–97% of the time. y ends 40% of all words. This degree of positional constraint is stronger than in any known natural language alphabet.

3 Word-Level Structure

3.1 Word Length Distribution

Figure 2: Word length distribution. Peak at 5 characters (24.4%). 72% of all tokens are 4–7 characters.

Metric	Value	Length	Examples
Corpus mean	5.08 chars	1 char	s, y, o, l, r
Corpus median	5 chars	2 chars	ol, ar, or, al, dy
Corpus mode	5 chars	5 chars (peak)	daiin, chedy, shedy, qokal
Vocabulary mean	6.67 chars	10+ chars	opchedaiin, qokeodaiin

Observation: Tight length clustering

72% of tokens fall in the 4–7 character range. The vocabulary mean (6.67) exceeds the corpus mean (5.08) because rare words tend to be longer.

3.2 Extreme Words

1-character words		2-character words	
Word	Count	Word	Count
s	309	ol	552
y	296	ar	400
o	193	or	380
l	189	al	256
r	167	dy	233
d	63	am	85

Word	Length	Count
syoraiinykeeolothedy	22	1
shdydchdchsychsyotchdy	21	1
okeedydchsychsotchdy	20	1
chdyolchyykchyykedy	19	1
yteychkeeodypchedpy	19	1
dteodoiinsaroqoches	19	1
lshedarydalshalshy	18	1

Observation: Long words are all hapax

Every word longer than 17 characters appears exactly once. Words above ~20 characters likely represent transcription run-ons (missed word boundaries).

3.3 Word Boundaries

Word-initial			Word-final		
Char	Count	%	Char	Count	%
o	7,032	20.6	y	13,831	40.5
c	6,298	18.4	n	5,589	16.3
q	5,191	15.2	l	5,332	15.6
s	4,134	12.1	r	5,040	14.7
d	3,221	9.4	o	1,190	3.5
Top-5 coverage:		75.7%	Top-4 coverage:		87.1%

Table 9: Word-initial and word-final character distributions.

Observation: Word endings are extremely concentrated

Four characters—y, n, l, r—end 87.1% of all words. y alone ends 40.5% of tokens. No known natural writing system shows a single letter ending more than ~20% of words.

Observation: Disjoint initial/final sets

The word-initial set (o, c, q, s, d) and word-final set (y, n, l, r) share only o at low rates. This near-complete disjunction is stronger than any known natural writing system.

3.3.1 Cross-Word Boundary Transitions

End	Start	Count	End	Start	Count
y	q	3,583	l	c	1,186
y	o	2,482	r	c	1,106
y	c	1,884	l	o	995
n	o	1,527	r	a	847
n	c	1,460	l	s	821
y	d	1,441	n	s	819
r	o	1,286			
y	s	1,271			

Table 10: Most frequent cross-word boundary character bigrams. $y \rightarrow q$ dominates (3,583 occurrences).

3.4 Zipf’s Law and Frequency Bands

Figure 3: Log-log plot of word rank vs. frequency. $\alpha = 0.944$, $R^2 = 0.925$. The distribution has a heavier head and thinner tail than a perfect power law.

Frequency band	Types	Tokens	% tokens	Mean len	Examples
100+	56	12,070	35.6%	4.04	daiin, ol, chedy, aiin
21–100	192	8,067	23.8%	4.94	okeedy, oty, oteey, oky
6–20	508	5,237	15.4%	5.13	tchey, shaiin, chety
2–5	1,453	4,037	11.9%	5.85	shory, okan, ydain
1 (hapax)	4,520	4,520	13.3%	6.66	fachys, ataiin, ase

Table 11: Word types and tokens by frequency band. 56 word types (0.8% of vocabulary) generate 35.6% of all tokens.

Observation: Extreme concentration at the top

56 words produce over a third of the text. High-frequency words average 4.04 characters; hapax words average 6.66 characters—a length–frequency correlation steeper than in most natural languages.

3.5 Prefix–Suffix Morphology

Prefix	Types	Tokens	% tokens	Top words
ch-	921	5,521	16.3	chedy, chol, chey
qo-	698	5,076	15.0	qokeey, qokeedy, qokain
o- (bare)	726	3,049	9.0	o, otaiin, otedy
sh-	485	2,997	8.8	shedy, shey, shol
da-	191	2,056	6.1	daiin, dar, dal
ok-	279	2,006	5.9	okaiin, okeey, okal
ol-	254	1,463	4.3	ol, oly, olaiin
s- (not sh)	244	1,137	3.4	s, saiin, sar

Table 12: Major prefix families. The top 8 prefixes account for 68.8% of all tokens.

Suffix	Types	Tokens	% tokens	Top words
-y (bare)	1,033	4,163	12.3	y, chy, qoky
-edy	371	3,882	11.4	chedy, shedy, qokeedy
-aiin	420	3,542	10.4	daiin, aiin, qokaiin
-ol	390	2,674	7.9	chol, shol, cheol
-dy (not -edy)	588	2,212	6.5	dy, chdy, chody
-ar	425	2,000	5.9	dar, qokar, otar
-ey (not -eey)	327	1,894	5.6	chey, shey, qokeey
-eey	231	1,680	5.0	qokeey, cheey, okeey
-ain (not -aiin)	249	1,577	4.6	qokain, dain, okain
-am	210	640	1.9	dam, am, otam

Table 13: Major suffix families. The top 10 suffixes account for 71.5% of all tokens.

Observation: Combinatorial prefix–suffix system

8 prefixes and 10 suffixes account for 69% and 72% of all tokens respectively. The same suffixes recur across prefix families (ch-edy, sh-edy, qok-edy; ch-ol, sh-ol; da-iin, qoka-iin).

Word	Freq	Prefix	Core	Suffix
daiin	794	da-		-iin
chedy	481	ch-		-edy
shedy	410	sh-		-edy
chol	374	ch-		-ol
chey	332	ch-		-ey
qokeey	298	qok-		-eey
qokeedy	296	qok-		-eedy
qokain	272	qok-	e	-ain
qokedy	268	qok-		-edy
qokaiin	262	qok-		-aiin

Table 14: Sample decompositions. 93.2% of the top 500 words decompose into known prefix + suffix with minimal core.

3.6 Word Length and Repetitiveness

Len	Tokens	Types	TTR	Top-5%	Top 5 words
1	1,141	15	0.013	90.5	s, y, l, o, r
2	2,261	87	0.038	72.7	ol, or, ar, dy, al
3	3,257	275	0.084	27.8	dar, dal, chy, qol, sho
4	6,192	628	0.101	26.3	aiin, chol, chey, shey, chor
5	8,452	1,177	0.139	24.0	daiin, chedy, shedy, qokal, cheey
6	6,546	1,505	0.230	17.9	qokeey, qokain, qokedy, okaiin, otaiin
7	3,795	1,428	0.376	19.9	qokeedy, qokaiin, qotaiin, qo-teedy
8	1,494	926	0.620	11.1	chodaiin, qokchedy, qopchedy
9+	776	680	0.876	—	Almost all hapax

Table 15: Repetitiveness by word length. Short words are extremely repetitive; 9+ character words are almost all unique.

Observation: Sharp TTR gradient with length

1-character words have TTR=0.013 (15 types generating 1,141 tokens). By 9+ characters, TTR reaches 0.876. The transition from highly repetitive to almost-all-unique happens abruptly around length 7–8.

3.6.1 Word Length Autocorrelation

Figure 4: Word-length autocorrelation. Lag-1 shows a spike at +0.141; lags 2–10 plateau around +0.04.

Observation: Word lengths cluster

Lag-1 autocorrelation of +0.141 means adjacent words tend to have similar lengths. Short words follow short words 31% more often than chance (25.6% vs 19.6%); long words follow long words 38% more often (24.7% vs 17.9%).

4 Line and Paragraph Structure

4.1 Lines and Paragraphs

Metric	Mean	Median	Min	Max
Words per line	7.1	7	1	55
Words per paragraph [†]	139	88	9	576
Lines per paragraph [†]	5.3	4	1	32

Table 16: [†]Paragraph statistics use the 244 multi-line text paragraphs. The transcription contains 780 paragraph markers, but 536 of these are single-line entries (labels, annotations, or short fragments).

Figure 5: Words per line distribution. Peak at 7–10 words per line.

4.2 Word Position Effects

Certain words strongly prefer line-initial or line-final positions.

Line-initial biased				Line-final biased			
Word	Init.	Total	Enrich.	Word	Final	Total	Enrich.
sain	33	60	4.8x	am	50	64	6.8x
sol	32	59	4.7x	oly	39	57	6.0x
sar	30	66	4.0x	dam	48	74	5.7x
saiin	53	117	4.0x	dy	81	241	2.9x
dor	19	62	2.7x	cthy	26	101	2.2x
sho	31	120	2.2x	oty	23	99	2.0x
dain	48	204	2.0x	oky	21	92	2.0x
y	63	276	2.0x	dal	44	204	1.9x

Table 17: Words with strongest positional bias. Enrichment = observed rate / expected rate.

Observation: Line-initial words start with **s** or **d**

The most line-initial-enriched words—*sain*, *sol*, *sar*, *saiin*, *sho*—all begin with **s** or **d**.

Observation: Line-final words end with **m** or **y**

The word *am* appears line-finally 78% of the time (50 of 64 occurrences). *dam* appears line-finally 65% of the time.

4.2.1 Paragraph Boundaries

Paragraph-initial words are overwhelmingly *gallows*-initial (the four tall characters *k, t, p, f* in EVA notation):

Paragraph starters		Paragraph ends	
Word	Count	Word	Count
pchor	3	daiin	16
pchedar	3	shedy	4
tchedy	3	chor	3
kooiin	2	otal	3
koary	2	chey	3
pol	2	ary	3

Table 18: Top paragraph-initial and paragraph-final words. 224 unique starters, 200 unique ends.

Observation: Gallows characters dominate paragraph starts

77.3% of paragraph-initial words begin with a gallows character (*k, t, p, f*), compared to 7.7% of other words—a 10.1x enrichment.

4.3 The Jaccard Anomaly

The line-to-line Jaccard similarity index measures how many words consecutive lines share.

Corpus	Mean Jaccard	Note
English prose	0.28	Function words shared across lines
Latin prose	0.30	Inflected function words still repeat
Voynich (VMS)	0.032	10x below natural language
Random (vocab=8000)	0.01	No structure

VMS Overall		By Section	
Metric	Value	Section	Mean J
Mean	0.032	Biological	0.051
Median	0.000	Text-only	0.035
Std dev	0.048	Pharma	0.031
Line pairs	3,388	Herbal	0.025
		Cosmological	0.022
		Astronomical	0.006

Observation: Median Jaccard is zero

Most consecutive line pairs share *no words at all*. The mean of 0.032 is pulled up by the minority of pairs sharing 1–2 words.

Observation: No distance decay

Jaccard at distance 1 (0.030), distance 2 (0.029), distance 3 (0.026), distance 5 (0.026). Lines 5 apart share as few words as adjacent lines.

4.4 Word N-Gram Statistics

The following word-level analyses use paragraph text only (33,931 tokens, 6,729 types), excluding labels, circular, and radial text.

<i>n</i> -gram	Total	Unique	Hapax	Hapax%	$H(n)/n$ bits
1-word	33,931	6,729	4,520	67.2%	10.181
2-word	33,930	28,713	26,266	91.5%	7.306
3-word	33,929	33,747	33,586	99.5%	5.013
4-word	33,928	33,927	33,926	100.0%	3.763

Table 19: Word *n*-gram statistics. Hapax rate reaches 100% by 4-word groups.

Observation: Word trigrams are almost all unique

99.5% of 3-word sequences appear exactly once. The most frequent word trigram occurs only 5 times in 33,929 opportunities.

Word pair	Count	Word pair	Count
s aiin	55	chedy qokeey	19
or aiin	51	chedy qokain	18
chol daiin	32	qokeedy qokeedy	18
chol chol	24	shedy qokain	17
ar aiin	24	s ar	16
ol shedy	24	ar al	16
r aiin	22	shedy qokaiin	16
shedy qokedy	21	shedy qokeedy	15
ol chedy	21	qokedy qokedy	15

Table 20: Top word bigrams. Self-repetitions like “chol chol” (24x) and “qokeedy qokeedy” (18x) are prominent.

Observation: Strong word-to-word predictability

Conditional entropy $H(w_2|w_1) = 4.43$ bits vs $H(w_1) = 10.18$ bits. The ratio 0.435 means knowing the previous word reduces uncertainty about the next by 56%—far stronger than typical natural language (ratio ≈ 0.7 – 0.8).

4.5 Paragraph Length Distribution

Figure 6: Paragraph length distribution. Most paragraphs fall in the 51–100 word range. The long right tail includes f103–f116 pages.

Observation: Long paragraphs

Mean paragraph length is 139 EVA words, with a median of 88. This is 2–4x longer than typical prose paragraphs in natural languages (30–80 words).

5 Repetition Patterns

5.1 Line-Level Exact and Near Repetition

Metric	Value
Total lines analyzed	3,889
Lines with exact word repeats	987 (25.4%)
Lines with near-repeats (edit distance 1)	2,167 (55.7%)

Observation: Majority of lines contain near-repeats

55.7% of all lines contain at least one pair of words differing by a single character.

Word 1	Word 2	Count	Word 1	Word 2	Count
ol	or	99	ol	qol	49
chedy	shedy	88	chol	chor	46
aiin	daiin	70	chol	shol	36
qokeedy	qokeey	65	chey	shey	34
ar	or	61	chdy	chedy	33
qokedy	qokeedy	60	chedy	lchedy	33
shedy	shey	60	dol	ol	32
daiin	dain	56	okedy	qokedy	31
chedy	chey	52			

Table 21: Most common minimal pairs (edit distance 1) co-occurring in the same line.

Observation: Systematic single-character variation

The most common near-repeat pairs show consistent patterns: initial-character swaps (chedy~shedy, chol~shol), final-character changes (shedy~shey, daiin~dain), and prefix addition/removal (aiin~daiin, okedy~qokedy).

5.2 Consecutive Runs and Near-Chains

Across 33,931 tokens, there are **270 consecutive runs** (identical word repeated 2+ times) containing 550 tokens (1.6% of the corpus).

Run length	Count	Pct of runs	Cumulative tokens
2 (word repeated once)	261	96.7%	522
3 (word repeated twice)	8	3.0%	24
4 (word repeated thrice)	1	0.4%	4
Total	270		550

Nine lines contain a word repeated three or more times consecutively:

Folio	Word	Run	Line context
f75r.13	qokedy	4	pchedy.keedy. qokedy.qokedy.qokedy.qokedy .qokain.olstedy
f8v.8	chol	3	okcholksh. chol.chol.chol .cthaiin.dain
f14v.6	dy	3	qoty.choky.cthy.chokchy. dy.dy.dy .chckhy.dchyd.n
f40r.9	okaiin	3	taiin.ol.olaiin.or.dain. okaiin.okaiin.okaiin .daram
f47r.7	chol	3	schesy.kchor.cthaiin. chol.chol.chol .chor.ey
f76r.5	or	3	qokedy.qokeey. or.or.or .chkorol.otey.qokedy
f79v.19	qokedy	3	shy.qolar.shey. qokedy.qokedy.qokedy .dar.olka...
f104v.27	sheol	3	pchoror.shor. sheol.sheol.sheol .qokchedy.chdor
f108v.40	qokeedy	3	daiin.sheal. qokeedy.qokeedy.qokeedy .qotey.qokeey

Table 22: All lines containing 3+ consecutive identical words.

5.2.1 Near-Consecutive Chains

Extending to chains where each adjacent pair is identical or edit distance 1 reveals 121 chains of length 3+:

Folio	Locus	Length	Words in chain
f102v2	19	6	o.l.o.r.o.l
f75r	38	5	qokeedy.qokeedy.qokedy.qokedy.qokeedy
f31r	10	4	okedy.okedy.qokedy.qokeedy
f42r	13	4	shol.shot.shol.shol
f42r	21	4	shol.chol.chol.shol
f47r	7	4	chol.chol.chol.chor
f75r	13	4	qokedy.qokedy.qokedy.qokedy
f76r	34	4	shedy.shedy.shey.shedy
f84v	14	4	otedy.okedy.okedy.qokedy
f103v	24	4	olan.otan.otain.otain
f108r	42	4	okeey.qokeey.qokeedy.qokeey
f112r	37	4	olkedy.okedy.okeey.okeedy

Table 23: Longest near-consecutive chains (edit distance ≤ 1 between adjacent pairs).

5.3 Repetition by Section and Frequency Band

Section	Words	Runs	Rate per 1,000 words
Biological	5,963	58	9.7
Pharmaceutical	2,328	19	8.2
Herbal	11,385	92	8.1
Text-only	2,276	17	7.5
Stars	11,609	82	7.1

Table 24: Consecutive repetition rate by section. Biological pages have the highest concentration.

Word	Runs	Max run	Freq	% tokens in runs
chol	22	3	374	12.3%
qokeedy	17	3	296	11.8%
qokedy	12	4	268	10.1%
qokeey	12	2	298	8.1%
daiin	10	2	793	2.5%
ol	9	2	519	3.5%
shedy	9	2	409	4.4%
chedy	9	2	481	3.7%
ar	8	2	318	5.0%
chor	7	2	209	6.7%
dy	7	3	241	6.2%

Table 25: Words most frequently involved in consecutive runs. The qo- prefix family collectively accounts for 56 of 270 runs (21%).

Observation: Consecutive repetition targets mid-frequency words

The overall consecutive-repetition rate (8.0 per 1,000 words) is 0.4x the rate expected from random Zipfian draws (18.9/1,000). Yet when runs *do* occur, they involve medium-frequency content words (chol, qokeedy, qokedy) at rates of 10–12%, while the highest-frequency words (daiin, ol) participate at only 2.5–3.5%.

5.4 Word Clustering and Most Repetitive Pages

Word	Count	Med. gap	Exp. gap	Ratio	Pattern
<i>Most clustered (bursty):</i>					
chotchy	12	86	2,828	0.030	Appears in tight clusters
shecthy	18	191	1,885	0.101	Page/section specific
lkain	34	116	998	0.116	Concentrated burst
<i>Most dispersed (evenly spread):</i>					
ytain	10	5,734	3,393	1.690	Spread wider than expected
ls	11	3,310	3,085	1.073	Near-uniform distribution

Table 26: Word clustering analysis. Ratio < 1.0 = bursty; > 1.0 = dispersed.

Observation: Extreme burst behavior

The most clustered words have median gaps 7–30x smaller than expected. `chotch` (12 occurrences) has a median gap of 86 words vs an expected 2,828—it appears almost exclusively in one or two passages.

Folio	Words	Unique	TTR	Consec	Top repeated words
f76r	559	258	0.462	8	shedy(28), chedy(24), chey(12)
f84v	321	152	0.474	2	shedy(17), ol(14), okedy(14)
f75r	408	197	0.483	7	qokain(21), qokeedy(17), shedy(16)
f116r	553	272	0.492	3	qokain(18), shey(17), chedy(15)
f77v	321	163	0.508	4	shedy(17), qokedy(17), qokal(17)
f108v	576	296	0.514	11	qokeedy(28), qokeey(21), aiin(13)

Table 27: The six most repetitive pages by TTR. All are from the Biological or Stars sections.

5.4.1 Case Study: f42r End-of-Page Repetition

The last four lines of folio f42r (Herbal section):

```

Line 20:  shol.chol.shoky.okol.sho.chol.shol.chal
Line 21:  shol.chol.chol.shol.oiin.s.odan
Line 22:  kchain.chos.ckhain.choro.r.chaiin
Line 23:  okchol.shol.kolschees

```

Observation: f42r ends with concentrated chol/shol repetition

13 of 20 words (65%) in the final four lines are variants of `chol/shol`. This density of near-identical words is far beyond what appears earlier on the same page.

6 Text Types and Layout Contexts

Words in the VMS appear in four layout contexts.

Type	Words	Unique	TTR	AvgLen
Paragraph	34,314	7,472	0.218	5.10
Circular	2,372	1,125	0.474	4.78
Label	1,186	860	0.725	5.30
Radial	350	281	0.803	5.26

Observation: Labels are almost all unique

Labels have TTR=0.725—nearly every label is a distinct word. Radial text is even higher (0.803). Paragraph text drives all repetition (TTR=0.218, 90% of tokens).

6.1 Label vs Paragraph Vocabulary

Type	Tokens	Types	TTR	Mean len
Paragraph	33,931	6,729	0.198	4.94
Label	258	180	0.698	3.90
Shared types	108 (1.6% of combined vocabulary)			
Label-only types	72 (40% of label vocabulary)			
Jaccard overlap	0.016			

Word	Top label words		Label-exclusive	
	Labels	Paragraphs	Word	Count
o	12	148	x	3
s	12	303	olkeedal	2
y	11	276	ios	1
d	7	51	otodara	1
f	5	1	oparairdly	1
e	5	2	salf	1

Table 28: Labels are dominated by single-character words. 72 label types never appear in paragraph text.

Observation: Labels are disjoint from paragraphs

Jaccard overlap is 0.016. Labels are shorter (mean 3.9 vs 4.9 chars), dominated by single-character words, and show different character frequencies: higher a (+4.3%), l (+3.3%), r (+3.0%); lower e (-4.4%), h (-4.1%).

7 Manuscript Sections and Currier Languages

The manuscript has 8 identified illustration types. Each section exhibits distinct statistical properties.

7.1 Section Statistics

Figure 7: Word count by manuscript section. Stars and Herbal dominate (>57% combined).

Section	Words	Unique	TTR	AvgLen	Top Word
Stars	11,644	3,304	0.284	5.21	aiin (218)
Herbal	10,916	3,620	0.332	5.06	daiin (412)
Biological	6,327	1,488	0.235	5.05	ol (222)
Pharmaceutical	2,561	1,154	0.451	5.09	daiin (95)
Text-only	2,358	986	0.418	4.85	or (44)
Cosmological	2,227	1,108	0.497	4.71	ar (51)
Zodiac	1,314	773	0.588	5.30	ar (28)
Astronomical	875	613	0.701	5.25	s (14)

Table 29: Per-section statistics. TTR ranges from 0.235 (Biological) to 0.701 (Astronomical)—a 3x variation.

<p>Observation: 3x TTR variation across sections</p> <p>Biological (0.235) vs Astronomical (0.701) differ by a factor of 3. This reflects genuinely different vocabulary usage: Biological text reuses the same words heavily; Astronomical text uses almost entirely unique words.</p>
<p>Observation: Section-specific top words</p> <p>daiin dominates Herbal/Pharma but is absent from the Astronomical top-10. ol dominates Biological. ar is most common in Cosmological/Zodiac.</p>

7.2 Section Vocabulary Overlap

	Astro	Bio	Cosmo	Herbal	Pharma	Stars	Text	Zodiac
Astro	—	.142	.199	.106	.173	.115	.189	.171
Bio		—	.187	.143	.157	.191	.227	.146
Cosmo			—	.138	.183	.171	.213	.176
Herbal				—	.150	.204	.154	.103
Pharma					—	.163	.191	.153
Stars						—	.185	.127
Text							—	.162

Table 30: Jaccard vocabulary overlap between sections. Highest: Bio–Text (0.227). Lowest: Herbal–Zodiac (0.103). No pair shares more than a quarter of their vocabulary.

7.3 Page-to-Page Vocabulary Coherence

Page distance	Mean Jaccard
1 (adjacent)	0.108
2	0.096
3	0.092
5	0.091
10	0.087

Table 31: Vocabulary overlap decays only 19% from adjacent pages to distance-10.

Transition type	Mean Jaccard
Same-section transitions (185 pairs)	0.112
Cross-section transitions (19 pairs)	0.068

Observation: Cross-section transitions break coherence

Cross-section page pairs have 40% lower Jaccard (0.068 vs 0.112). Three page transitions share literally zero vocabulary—all at section boundaries.

Observation: Weak distance decay

Within sections, vocabulary is relatively stable regardless of page distance—Jaccard drops only from 0.108 to 0.087 over 10 pages.

7.4 Currier Language A vs Language B

Prescott Currier [Currier(1976)] identified two statistically distinct “languages” in the manuscript. Language A predominates in the Herbal section; Language B dominates Biological, Stars, and Pharmaceutical sections.

Metric	Language A	Language B
Total tokens	11,221	22,399
Unique types	3,135	4,646
Type-token ratio	0.279	0.207
Mean word length	4.73 chars	5.05 chars
Hapax rate	68.5%	67.6%

#	Lang A	Count	#	Lang B	Count
1	daiin	495	1	chedy	479
2	chol	275	2	ol	409
3	s	202	3	shedy	406
4	chor	178	4	aiin	356
5	dy	125	5	qokeedy	296
6	shol	116	6	daiin	294
7	chy	116	7	qokain	268
8	y	109	8	qokedy	267
9	ol	109	9	qokeey	257
10	or	108	10	ar	254

Table 32: Top 10 words by Currier language. A favors gallows-initial words (ch-, sh-); B favors qo- prefixed words and -edy/-eey suffixes.

Overall character frequency				Word-initial character			
Char	A %	B %	Δ	Char	A %	B %	Δ
e	6.8	12.0	+5.2 B	c	24.9	15.2	−9.7 A
o	15.8	11.6	−4.2 A	d	14.9	6.6	−8.3 A
h	11.6	8.4	−3.1 A	q	9.9	18.0	+8.1 B
c	9.1	6.0	−3.0 A	o	16.9	22.4	+5.5 B
d	5.7	7.4	+1.7 B	l	0.8	5.8	+5.0 B
q	2.1	3.6	+1.5 B	a	2.7	6.4	+3.7 B

Table 33: Character frequency differences between Currier A and B.

Observation: Nearly disjoint vocabularies

Jaccard vocabulary overlap between A and B is 0.166—they share barely one-sixth of their combined vocabulary. B is 2x larger, has longer words, and is more repetitive.

Observation: Different character profiles

Language B uses *e* at nearly double the rate of A (12.0% vs 6.8%). Language A has far more *o*, *c*, and *h*. At word-initial position, *c* begins 24.9% of A-words but only 15.2% of B-words; *q* begins 18.0% of B-words vs 9.9% of A-words.

8 The Stars Section: Folios f103–f116

Folios f103r through f116r form a visually distinctive block of 23 pages: dense, continuous text with no illustrations, organized in long unbroken columns. All are classified as Language B.

Metric	f103–f116	Rest of MS
Folios	23	180
Total tokens	10,860	23,071
Mean words per line	10.1	8.2
Lines with 11+ words	547 (50.6%)	506 (18.0%)
Mean paragraph length (words)	434.4	105.3
Paragraphs with 81+ words	25 (100%)	112 (51.1%)
Unique types	3,047	5,002
Type-token ratio	0.281	0.217
Mean word length (chars)	5.20	4.82
Jaccard overlap with rest	0.196	
Types only in f103–f116	1,727	

Table 34: f103–f116 vs. the rest of the manuscript.

Observation: Paragraphs 4x longer than elsewhere

Mean paragraph length is 434 words vs 105 elsewhere. Lines are 23% longer. Over half of all lines contain 11+ words—compared to 18% elsewhere.

Observation: Partially distinct vocabulary

1,727 word types appear exclusively in f103–f116. The character *e* appears at 13.0% vs 9.2% elsewhere—the single largest character frequency difference, consistent with Currier B.

#	f103–f116	Count	#	Rest of MS	Count
1	aiin	210	1	daiin	673
2	chedy	198	2	ol	410
3	qokeey	159	3	chol	311
4	ar	148	4	shedy	292
5	al	138	5	chedy	283
6	qokeedy	136	6	or	280
7	chey	125	7	s	275
8	daiin	120	8	aiin	239
9	qokaiin	120	9	dar	235
10	shedy	117	10	dy	229

Table 35: Top 10 words: f103–f116 vs. rest. *aiin* is #1 in f103–f116 but #8 elsewhere.

9 Anomalous Folios and Patterns

9.1 The Word “daiin”

Property	Value
Total occurrences	798 (2.09% of all tokens)
Rank	#1 most frequent word
Paragraph start rate	0.14% (nearly absent)
Paragraph end rate	4.05% (2x average)
Herbal section rate	3.77%
Zodiac section rate	0.91%

Observation: “daiin” avoids paragraph starts

“daiin” appears as a paragraph-final word at 4.05% (2x the average word’s rate) but as a paragraph-initial word at only 0.14%—behaving as a closing element. Its corpus rate varies 4x across sections (Herbal 3.8% vs Zodiac 0.9%), indicating section-dependent usage.

9.2 f57v: The 17-Symbol Ring Sequence

Folio f57v is a cosmological diagram with concentric rings of text. The second outermost ring contains a sequence of 17 symbols that repeats 4 times:

Pos	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Rep 1	o	l	[d;j]	r	v	x	k	m	f	@169v	t	r	@170	@171	y	I	@172
Rep 2	o	l	d	r	v	x	k	m	f	@169v	t	r	@170	@171	y	c	@172
Rep 3	o	l	d	r	v	x	k	m	p	@169v	t	r	@170	@171	y	c	@172
Rep 4	o	l	d	r	v	x	k	m	p	@169v	t	r	@170	@171	y	c	@172

Table 36: The 17-symbol repeating sequence. Bold marks positions that vary. @-codes denote non-standard characters not found in regular EVA text.

The sequence varies at exactly three positions:

- **Position 3:** uncertain reading in repetition 1, d in repetitions 2–4.
- **Position 9:** f in repetitions 1–2, p in repetitions 3–4 (both gallows characters).
- **Position 16:** I in repetition 1 only, c in repetitions 2–4.

Observation: 17-symbol near-mechanical repetition

Only 3 of 68 symbols vary across the 4 repetitions. Four of the 17 symbols per cycle (@169v, @170, @171, @172) are non-standard characters not attested in the main body text.

9.3 f49v: The Numbered Letter Column

Folio f49v features a vertical column of 26 single letters or symbols down the left margin, with numbers 1–5 written adjacent:

#	Sym	#	Sym	#	Sym
1	f	10	o	19	y
2	o	11	@192	20	e
3	r	12	y	21	@140
4	y	13	e	22	d
5	e	14	@140	23	y
6	@140	15	@164	24	e
7	k	16	p	25	k
8	s	17	o	26	y
9	p	18	@192		

Table 37: The 26 column entries on f49v. @-codes denote non-standard characters.

Observation: Numbered repeating column

The column contains a 6-symbol repeating core (p o @192 y e @140) at positions 9–14 and 16–21. Three non-standard characters appear (@140 three times, @192 twice, @164 once). The physical numbering 1–5 is unique in the manuscript.

9.4 f66r: Paired Columns

Folio f66r (Text-only section) contains two vertical columns before the paragraph text. The first (lines 1–15) contains 15 short words; the second (lines 16–49) contains 34 single letters or symbols.

Word column (lines 1–15)		Letter column (16–49)	
#	Word	#	Symbol
1	rary	16	y
2	sals	17	o
3	qor	18	s
4	dary	19	sh
5	ykeol	20	y
6	saly	21	d
7	salf	22	o
8	fary	23	f
9	qotesy	24	@169
10	ykaly	25	x
11	doly	26	air
12	saiin	27	d
13	qokal	28	sh
14	qolsa	29	y
15	raral	30	f
		31	f
		32–49	y, o, d, s, f, c, @172, x, t, o, @195, l, r, t, o, x, p, d

Table 38: The two columns on f66r. The letter column shares non-standard symbols (@169, @172) with the f57v ring sequence.

Observation: Three folios with columnar/ring symbol sequences

f49v, f57v, and f66r each contain ordered sequences of individual symbols in non-standard layouts. All three concentrate non-standard characters (@-codes) not found in regular text. A transcription note on f66r explicitly cross-references f57v. This layout type appears nowhere else in the manuscript.

10 Discussion and Open Questions

Sections 1–9 present verifiable statistical observations. This section collects interpretive analysis and open questions that go beyond the data. The simulation results below are themselves reproducible; their *interpretation* is what remains open.

10.1 The Jaccard Anomaly and Homophone Models

The VMS line-to-line Jaccard of 0.032 is 10x below natural language. One class of explanation is **homophonic substitution**: if the same plaintext word maps to multiple ciphertext forms, surface repetition would be suppressed.

We simulated two models on synthetic Zipfian text (vocab=2,000, 5–12 words/line, 3,000 lines):

- **Model A (random assignment)**: Each token independently picks one of k homophones.
- **Model B (deliberate avoidance)**: The scribe tracks used forms and picks different ones for adjacent lines.

Figure 8: Jaccard index under homophone expansion. Model A matches VMS at $k=3$; Model B overshoots at $k=2$.

k	Model A: Random				Model B: Deliberate Avoidance			
	J	TTR	Vocab	Hapax	J	TTR	Vocab	Hapax
1	0.068	0.073	1,863	0.16	0.068	0.073	1,863	0.16
2	0.043	0.123	3,132	0.32	0.004	0.123	3,132	0.32
3	0.031	0.159	4,056	0.40	0.006	0.160	4,082	0.41
5	0.021	0.212	5,413	0.51	0.005	0.211	5,387	0.51
10	0.011	0.288	7,361	0.60	0.003	0.287	7,317	0.60
20	0.005	0.369	9,428	0.69	0.002	0.368	9,404	0.68
VMS	0.032	0.224	8,543	0.71	0.032	0.224	8,543	0.71

Table 39: Simulation results. No single expansion factor k matches all four VMS statistics simultaneously.

Key findings from the simulation:

- Random homophony at $k=3$ matches $J=0.031$, but $TTR=0.159$ vs VMS’s 0.224.
- Deliberate avoidance at $k=2$ produces $J=0.004$ —8x below VMS. Perfect avoidance is too effective.
- No single k matches Jaccard, TTR, vocabulary size, and hapax rate simultaneously.
- A more complex model—non-uniform homophony varying by word frequency—may be required.

10.2 Encoding Granularity

If each EVA word encodes one plaintext word, then VMS paragraphs average 139 words—far longer than typical prose (30–80 words). Under a verbose encoding where 2–2.5 EVA words correspond to one plaintext word, paragraph lengths become 56–70 words, within plausible range for technical text.

Evidence for sub-word encoding: paragraph lengths become plausible; strong word-to-word predictability ($H(w_2|w_1)/H(w_1) = 0.44$); top-30 character bigrams cover 79% of text. Evidence against: word-trigram hapax rate is 99.5% (higher than expected if 3-word groups formed “real words”); the word-level Zipf distribution is well-formed.

10.3 Open Questions

1. **What mechanism produces $J=0.032$?**

Neither uniform random homophony nor deliberate avoidance matches all VMS statistics simultaneously. A model with non-uniform homophony (varying k by word frequency) has not yet been tested.

2. **Why is character entropy so low?**

$H_1=2.83$ bits/char is 15% below English. Only 39% of possible character bigrams are used, and 30 bigrams cover 79% of text. If character bigrams are the actual encoding units, the effective alphabet is ~ 30 symbols and the effective word length is roughly half the EVA character count.

3. **Why does Biological text have the lowest TTR (0.235)?**

The Biological section is the most repetitive, with f76r as the single most repetitive page (TTR=0.462).

4. **What produces systematic minimal pairs?**

55.7% of lines contain near-repeat pairs (edit distance 1). Top pairs (ol~or, chedy~shedy, aiin~daiin) differ by exactly one character in consistent positions.

5. **What is the relationship between Currier A and B?**

Jaccard overlap is only 0.166. Language B has longer words, more qo- prefixes, and different dominant suffixes. Are these two encoding schemes, two dialects, two scribes, or two registers?

6. **Why does am appear line-finally 78% of the time?**

The word am occurs 64 times, with 50 at line-end (6.8x enrichment).

7. **Are prefixes and suffixes cipher components or linguistic morphemes?**

93% of common words decompose into known prefix + suffix. Currier A favors ch- / sh- prefixes while B favors qo- / ok-, suggesting prefixes carry content information.

8. **What are the columnar/ring sequences on f49v, f57v, and f66r?**

Three folios contain ordered sequences of individual symbols with non-standard characters not found in main text. Are these key tables, alphabets, or reference data?

A Statistical Definitions

Type-Token Ratio (TTR)

The number of unique word forms (types) divided by the total number of words (tokens): $TTR = \text{unique words} / \text{total words}$. A TTR of 1.0 means every word is unique; near 0 means extreme repetition.

Hapax Legomena

A word that appears exactly once in a corpus. The hapax rate is the fraction of vocabulary types that are singletons. Natural languages typically have hapax rates of 40–50% [Zipf(1935)].

Zipf's Law

In natural language, the frequency of a word is inversely proportional to its rank: $f(r) \propto r^{-\alpha}$, where $\alpha \approx 1.0$ [Zipf(1935)]. On a log-log plot, this produces a straight line. Fit quality is

measured by R^2 (1.0 = perfect).

Shannon Entropy

Measures the unpredictability of a symbol sequence [Shannon(1951)]: $H = -\sum_i p_i \log_2 p_i$. We use several variants:

- H_0 (unigram entropy): Treats each character independently.
- H_1 (bigram entropy per character): $H(c_1, c_2)/2$. Measures how much adjacent characters constrain each other.
- $H(c_2|c_1)$ (conditional entropy): $H(\text{bigrams}) - H(\text{unigrams})$. The residual uncertainty about the next character given the current one.
- H_2 (trigram entropy per character): $H(c_1, c_2, c_3)/3$.

Jaccard Similarity Index

Measures overlap between two sets [Jaccard(1908)]: $J(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$. Ranges from 0 (no overlap) to 1 (identical).

Edit Distance

The Levenshtein distance between two words is the minimum number of single-character insertions, deletions, or substitutions to transform one into the other. Words with distance 1 are **minimal pairs**.

Autocorrelation

Measures whether a sequence correlates with a shifted version of itself. For word lengths, lag- k autocorrelation asks whether the word k positions later tends to have similar length. Values range from -1 to $+1$.

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